

Pest resistance—insects

Gall midge (GM) resistance in traditional rice varieties of Manipur

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We tested 21 traditional rice varieties for resistance to GM *Orseolia oryzae*

Wood-Mason, a serious pest of rice in Manipur, in the field at Iroisemba 1986-88. Surekha and TN1 were the resistant and susceptible checks.

Seedlings at 1 mo old were transplanted in four 10-hill rows of each variety at 20- × 15-cm spacing. To ensure adequate pest pressure, TN1 was planted after every 20 rows. Plots were fertilized to induce tillering.

Damage (% silvershoots and % infested hills) was graded 45 d after transplanting.

In pooled 3-yr data, Phouren and Moirangphou khokngangbi show consistent resistance (see table). Akhanphou, Taothabi, Changphai, Kohima phou, Kakchengphou, and Chakhao amubi show less than 5% infestation. □

Reaction of traditional rice cultivars to GM. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1986-88.

Variety	1986		1987		1988		Mean		Resistance rating ^a
	Silver-shoots (%)	GM-infested hills (%)							
Moirangphou khokngangbi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Phouren	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Akhanphou	2	5	1	2	1	2	2	3	3
Chakhao amubi	2	5	2	2	1	2	2	3	3
Changphai	2	5	2	2	2	5	2	4	3
Kakchengphou	2	2	2	5	2	5	2	4	3
Kohima phou	1	2	4	5	2	5	3	4	3
Taothabi	2	5	2	2	1	2	2	3	3
Buman	7	15	6	15	4	10	6	13	5
Langmanphou	4	8	4	8	3	5	3	7	5
Changlei	6	15	6	12	5	10	6	12	5
Chiposelak	8	12	4	10	4	10	5	11	5
Keibuchirong	4	10	3	8	3	5	3	8	5
Moirangphou	3	5	4	8	6	20	4	11	5
Nahazing	8	15	5	12	4	10	6	12	5
Rarangma	4	12	3	8	4	10	4	10	5
Taothabi angouba	10	18	9	10	3	15	7	14	5
Kumbi phou	12	20	15	22	6	12	11	18	7
Sangsangba	10	2	12	28	5	10	9	21	7
Tadukan	7	22	9	25	6	20	7	22	7
Tangangkate	9	25	11	28	7	20	9	24	7
Surekha (resistant check)	2	5	3	5	1	2	2	4	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	16	55	21	74	10	30	16	53	9

^a Based on *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9: 0 = no damage, 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible.

Outbreak of blue beetle in India

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Blue beetle *Leptispa pygmaea* Baly. (Chrysomelidae: Coleoptera) has been considered a minor pest of rice, with incidences recorded in parts of Tamil Nadu, South Kanara, Mysore, Cochin, and Malabar District of Kerala.

A serious outbreak occurred in Kuzhithurai Division, Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu Nov-Dec 1988 (kumbapoo, or second season).

Incidence was very severe on about 50 ha of Ponmani during maximum tillering and panicle initiation.

The rice cultivation tract in Nattalam and Killiyur blocks is locally called Ela, which means low-lying rice area surrounded by hill and forest vegetation. The ricefields are situated in the valley, with coconut, banana, vegetable crops, and forest plantations on both

sides. The area is very fertile and has good irrigation from storage ponds.

We surveyed blue beetle incidence, damage, and life stages during its maximum feeding stage on 40 rice leaves sampled from 40 clumps. The pest in both larval and adult stage was found feeding on the upper surface of rice leaves, causing longitudinal white streaks of scraping. In severe attack, the leaves folded longitudinally and dried up. From a distance, the affected rice patch showed severe drying symptoms resembling that caused by